

VITAMIN C CONTENTS OF INDIAN FOODSTUFFS. CHILLIES (*CAPSICUM*).

By C. A. ROTHENBERG, H. S. SHAIK MAHAMUD and S. S. COWLAGI.

The ascorbic acid contents of several varieties of chillies (*Capsicum*) found around the city of Bombay have been determined. A modified method of Tillmans using a 2:6-dichlorophenolindophenol has been used. The reversibly oxidised ascorbic acid has been reduced by hydrogen sulphide. The values of ascorbic acid thus obtained are considerably higher. The ascorbic acid content of ripe chillies is greater than that of green ones. Chillies do not contain iron.

Though a large amount of work has been done on the vitamin content of foodstuffs, there is still a wide field for the standardisation of the vitamin contents of Indian plants and foodstuffs, especially in the different provinces where the same material contains varying amounts of the vitamins. It is also observed that different varieties of the same plant contain widely different amounts of the vitamin. This paper deals with the ascorbic acid content of chillies which are found round about the city of Bombay. The chillies for these experiments were obtained through the Superintendent of the Crawford market who had kindly arranged to supply us with the freshest material available in Bombay.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In estimating ascorbic acid, the micro-chemical method developed by Tillmans *et al* (*Z. untersuch. Lebensmit*, 1932, **63**, 1, 21, 276) as modified by Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 590) and Birch, Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 303) was followed. The above method of titration with 2:6-dichlorophenolindophenol does not hold good if iron is present in the extract of the vegetable matter. It is also known that phenols, cysteine, yeast extracts and tannins are interfering substances. It is further known that certain naturally occurring reducing agents such as glutathione and certain phenolic compounds tend to reduce the indicator in neutral or alkaline solutions. The titrations were, therefore, carried out in acid solution and the chillies were carefully tested for the presence of iron and phenolic bodies. For this purpose about 10 g. of chillies were cut into small pieces and were boiled in a dish with about 75 ml. of 3% hydrochloric acid. The boiling was continued till about two-thirds of the liquid

evaporated. This was then filtered and the filtrate tested for iron. No trace of iron was detected in any of the varieties of chillies examined. A portion of the above filtrate was used to detect the presence of phenolic and reducing bodies and none of the varieties gave the characteristic colour with ferric chloride or any precipitate with mercuric acetate.

In estimating ascorbic acid by Tillmans method we used a well known make of ascorbic acid as a standard.

The ascorbic acid solution was made by dissolving pure ascorbic acid in redistilled water. The solution was stored in the dark in the refrigerator in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. Under these conditions it was found to be fairly stable but daily standardisation was necessary as shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Date.	Ascorbic acid content in 10 ml. soln.
9-6-1937	0.8676 mg.
15-6-1937	0.7934
22-6-1937	0.7807
1-7-1937	0.7778

Though there is seen a marked fall in the ascorbic acid content of the solution over a period of seven days, it was found to be constant during the course of a day. For this reason, it is desirable to standardise the solution before any estimation of the vegetable extract is undertaken, though for subsequent titration during the day the strength of the solution is constant.

The standardisation was carried out in presence of dilute sulphuric acid against 0.01N-iodine solution using freshly prepared starch solution as indicator. The concentration of ascorbic acid was so adjusted that 1 ml. of 0.01N-iodine was required for 10 ml. of ascorbic acid solution. Each ml. of 0.01N-iodine is equivalent to 0.88 mg. of ascorbic acid.

The indicator solution was made by dissolving 0.1 g. of 2:6-dichlorophenolindophenol in 50 ml. of hot phosphate buffer solution of pH 7.2. When prepared in this way it is fairly stable, but like ascorbic acid this solution requires daily standardisation. Table II gives the range of the fall of the concentration of the indicator solution expressed in equivalents of ascorbic acid.

TABLE II.

Date.	Ascorbic acid equivalent of 1 ml. of the indicator solution.
9-6-1937	0.9947 mg.
15-6	0.9028
22-6	0.8685
1-7	0.7778

Thus a daily titration of the indicator solution with a standardised solution of the ascorbic acid solution gives the best results in the estimation of the extract. In standardising the indicator, it is necessary to preserve the same general conditions regarding acidity and dilution, which are present, while titrating the unknown ascorbic acid content of the vegetable extract. In the present case 0.05 ml. of the indicator solution from a 1 ml. microburette was run into a small conical flask to which were previously added 1 ml. of distilled water and 1 ml. of glacial acetic acid. This was then titrated against the ascorbic acid from a microburette till the red colour which the indicator immediately assumes in acid solution is just discharged. Special care was taken to see that the flask is constantly shaken during the titration and the whole operation is finished within 1-2 minutes.

Extraction.—About 30 g. of chillies were weighed after removing the stalks. The chillies were then ground on an Indian grinding stone. As the surfaces of the grinding stones are rough no sand is necessary and the material is obtained in a very finely divided pasty mass. During the process of grinding 5 ml. of 20 % trichloroacetic acid, 20 ml. of distilled water and 1 ml. of 0.1M-potassium cyanide were added gradually. Potassium cyanide was added following the observation of McHenry and Graham that it has the stabilising effect on the ascorbic acid present in the material. The finely ground pulp so obtained was centrifuged for 5-7 minutes at 3000 r. p. m. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the residue similarly extracted twice in the centrifuge cups with 17 ml. of 3% trichloroacetic acid and 5 drops of 0.1M-potassium cyanide. The volume of the combined supernatant liquid was measured and the liquid was filtered through a Buchner funnel.

The filtrate was then titrated from a microburette against 0.1 ml. of standard indicator solution to which 2 ml. of water and 2 ml. of glacial acetic acid were added following the observation of Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30) that the addition of acetic acid inhibits the spontaneous decolouration of the dye in the presence of trichloroacetic acid,

The indicator was diluted with water, following the observation of McHenry and Graham (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, **29**, 2013) that the time required for the given amount of trichloroacetic acid to decolourise a fixed amount of indophenol solution is considerably increased when the indophenol is diluted with 15-20 volumes of water and at the same dilution the time required for the reduction of the dye by ascorbic acid is only slightly prolonged. As in the previous case the titrations were carried out within 1-2 minutes. We have also observed, as did Ghosh and Guha, that a very faint pink colour persists at the end of the titration but the error from this source may be avoided by comparing the titration flask with a control. Table III gives typical results of a number of analyses of various chillies examined by us.

TABLE III.

Name of the varieties.	Condition of the chillies.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g.	
		By direct extraction.	By reduction of extract with H ₂ S.
Jadi mirchi (Panzel.) <i>Capsicum grossum</i>	4 days old	0.042	0.230
"	Fresh	0.061	0.431
"	"	0.168	0.495
"	"	0.095	0.572
"	Ripe	0.115	0.661
Long, light green variety	Fresh	0.046	0.303
"	"	0.047	0.328
Long, dark green shining variety	"	0.066	0.331
Lavangi, very small variety, <i>Capsicum minimum</i>	Ripe	0.101	0.248

In all our experiments green chillies were used in as fresh a condition as they could be available. Where ripe chilli is indicated they are red in colour and fully mature while others are green. The above values represent the more typical results from a number of analyses. From Table III it will be seen that the ascorbic acid content varies greatly with different varieties

of chillies. It is also seen that there is appreciable difference in different samples of the same variety. Among the varieties examined by us, the jadi mirchi or *Capsicum grossum* from Panvel gives higher vitamin content on the average. It is interesting to note that the ripe chillies contain a proportionately higher amount of the ascorbic acid. This is especially clear from Lavangi or *Capsicum minimum* in which case both the green and the ripe (red) samples were plucked at the same time from the tree and examined for ascorbic acid with the minimum delay. It seems that the formation of ascorbic acid attains the highest level in the ripe chillies.

Reduced and Reversibly Oxidised Ascorbic Acid.

Tillmans, Hirsch and Jackish observed that the titration value of cucumber extracts was considerably increased when the extracts were kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen sulphide for several hours. Similar results were obtained by McHenry and Graham in case of onions and carrots. In our experiments, the method of McHenry and Graham was followed. The chilly extract was diluted with an equal volume of water so that the concentration of trichloroacetic acid was 1.5 per cent. Hydrogen sulphide was then bubbled in for 10 minutes. The flask was tightly corked and left in the refrigerator overnight. Hydrogen sulphide was removed on the following day by passing a stream of carbon dioxide for two hours till there was no trace of sulphide. The ascorbic acid content was then estimated as previously stated. The results of this reduction of the partially oxidised ascorbic acid are given in the last column of Table III.

It will be seen that the value of the ascorbic acid after reduction is very considerable. There is also a rough proportionality between the free ascorbic acid and the ascorbic acid after reduction, in an inverse proportion. Thus where the free acid is low in concentration the reduced acid is considerably higher. It is thus interesting to note that the ascorbic acid always exists in the plant material as a reversibly oxidised derivative along with the free acid.